

HIJACK MARKETING: A SHARIA-COMPLIANT INSIGHT

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Article Info	ABSTRACT
<p>Article history: Received: 7 April 2024 Revised: 30 April 2024 Accepted: 15 May 2024 Published: 1 June 2024</p>	<p>This article explores hijack marketing from a Sharia-compliant perspective. Hijack marketing is when a company uses the media attention surrounding a novel occasion or problem to sell more products. This study aims to examine the application of hijack marketing techniques from a Sharia perspective. Data collection and analysis methods used in this qualitative study include document analysis and observation. Its objectives include investigating the idea of hijack marketing in product promotion and the Sharia-related problems connected to its application. It also aims to provide standards for designing marketing strategies using the Syarak viewpoint. The results of the study indicate that hijack marketing analysis is legitimate as long as it follows the Sharia guidelines.</p>
<p>Keywords: Hijack marketing Sharia-compliant perspective Data collection Qualitative study Syarak viewpoint</p> <p></p>	

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INTRODUCTION

A vital social activity that is inextricably linked to human existence is business. It includes buying and selling to satisfy everyday necessities, whether or not they are business owners (Zulkifli et al., 2015). One establishes a human connection through these exchanges. Islam, being a complete faith, establishes broad guidelines to guarantee that commercial endeavors satisfy requirements and avert the exploitation of people or the community. In Islam, business aims to achieve both material and spiritual benefits (Ali, 2014). The Arabic word for commerce is "al-tijarah," which emphasizes purchasing and selling transactions. The importance of commerce to humanity is emphasized in the Quran (Uddin, 2003). Academics argue that although people may decide not to get married, doing business is a given. While regulations governing certain acts of worship, such as prayer or fasting, differ from Islamic business law, which is based on rational goals, these acts also have purposes beyond mere compliance (Hassan, 2016). Scholars view business as a noble endeavor. Before getting married, the Prophet Muhammad and many of his companions were traders, demonstrating the importance of trade in society (Sidani & Al Ariss, 2015). Islam promotes charitable giving and business ventures (Rawashdeh et al., 2017). To prevent injury or exploitation, marketing and advertising strategies must adhere to Sharia standards. It is imperative for Muslim traders to conform to all-encompassing Islamic principles in all facets of their lives, including marketing strategies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The literature review includes the definition of business in Islam, the concept of Hijack Marketing, SEN Students with Learning Disabilities, and 21st-century Learning.

CONCEPT OF BUSINESS IN ISLAM

When business operations align with specific criteria, they are considered compliant with Islamic management, reflecting Islam's emphasis on comprehensive excellence that integrates management as a fundamental aspect. Deviating from this integration would mean contravening Islamic teachings. 'Muamalat,' as defined by (Salah & Alhabeeb, 2020), encompasses business transactions, service provision, and borrowing practices. Conversely, 'haram sources' denote individuals or entities that acquire funds unlawfully (Faridah Abdul Jabbar, 2011; Ibrahim et al., 2019; Nurhadi, 2019). This research examines transactions conducted through lawful means but sourced from activities or outcomes deemed illegal, such as opening wadi'ah accounts for employees of conventional banks or alcohol companies (Aden, 2019). Business owners are required to be committed Muslims, demonstrating their dedication to Allah SWT through their actions and relationships. In addition to pursuing financial gain, entrepreneurs fulfill their responsibilities under Fard al-Kifayah (Leong et al., 2024). Success in Islam entails achieving goals aligned with religious principles, necessitating managers to ensure success in this world and the hereafter. Quranic teachings underscore the integration of management into religious obligations. It is essential not to isolate business operations from Islam's holistic teachings, as Islamic business management becomes an obligation under fard al-Kifayah. Muslim managers must demonstrate that the Islamic business approach can effectively substitute conventional business practices.

CONCEPT OF HIJACK MARKETING

The core component of any kind of business is marketing (Morgan, 2012). Business owners or traders frequently use a wide range of marketing techniques, including public leaflet distribution, radio, TV, newspaper, and magazine advertising, among many others (McCole, 2004). A product won't be well-known, and making sales without marketing tactics will be difficult. Traders won't see a return on their investments if customers do not respond (Ulin, 2019). Nonetheless, even a recently founded company can become well known by using robust marketing techniques to draw clients who are prepared to buy the advertised goods. Marketing by hijacking is only one of several marketing strategies (Mason & Staude, 2009). Hijack marketing is the practice of a company or brand trying to use the media attention surrounding current events to its advantage. One of the most well-known and applauded instances is the Oreo product, which responded to the half-hour blackout during the 2013 Super Bowl with a tweet on their account that said, "You can still dunk in the dark"

(Dhawan & Joni, 2015). This kind of hijack marketing has plenty of potential for product recognition. However, if a company uses this strategy improperly, it may suffer losses or face legal action from some parties.

ADVERTISING IN ISLAM

Islamic advertising follows rules that are firmly ingrained in Islamic morality and ethics (Shafiq et al., 2017). The most important of these values is truthfulness (Siddiq), which calls on advertisements to present true information about their goods and services without using distortion or hyperbole (Ekramol Islam & Zahedul Alam, 2013). It is strictly forbidden to engage in deception (Tadlis), underscoring the significance of honesty and transparency in all advertising tactics. Furthermore, Islamic advertising encourages advertisers to refrain from using methods that denigrate people or belittle their modesty in order to uphold respect for human dignity (Izzah) (Abdul Cader, 2015). Furthermore, Islamic advertising forbids the promotion of illegal goods or services, such as alcohol or gambling, in favor of halal and socially valuable goods and services (Hasan, 2019; Shahabuddin et al., 2020). Ad content must be sensitive to cultural and religious values in order to respect different viewpoints and avoid offending anyone. Additionally, emphasis is placed on social responsibility (Mas'uliyah al-Ijtima'iyah), which calls for advertising to support charitable organizations and engage in moral corporate practices in order to favorably impact society.

RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

The findings of this study reveal three themes based on previous research on the use of hijack marketing methods to determine whether advertising methods comply with Islamic Shariah. The first theme is adherence to religious principles, the second is clear and accurate information, and the third is avoiding disclosure of faults.

Adhering to Religious Principles

Adhering to religious principles in business endeavors within Islamic contexts is deeply rooted in the teachings of the Quran and the Hadith. The Quranic verse from Surah Al-Maidah (5:88) emphasizes the importance of consuming what is lawful and reasonable while instilling in believers a sense of God-consciousness (Taqwa). Islam permits and encourages business activities, recognizing them as a legitimate means of livelihood. This encouragement is further reinforced by numerous verses and Hadiths that promote trade and commerce, with Prophet Muhammad himself acknowledging the significance of trade as a source of sustenance. For instance, the Hadith recorded in Tirmidhi illustrates the Prophet's recognition of the importance of trade, stating that "9/10 of sustenance comes from trade." Therefore, business serves as a crucial avenue for individuals to acquire wealth and goods, fulfilling personal and societal needs. However, the ethical conduct of business operations is paramount within Islamic principles. Conducting business per Shariah guidelines ensures that transactions are conducted ethically and with integrity, reflecting Allah's guidance and fostering trust among Muslim and non-Muslim consumers. Straying from these ethical boundaries can have detrimental consequences in this world and the Hereafter. Adhering to Shariah principles in business practices serves to promote fairness, justice, and righteousness, aligning with the overarching goal of seeking the pleasure of Allah. By upholding religious principles in business dealings, individuals and organizations can attain success in this life and secure blessings and rewards in the Hereafter.

Clear and Accurate Information

In the context of advertising and marketing, the principle of providing clear and accurate information is emphasized to ensure transparency and honesty in business dealings, as outlined in Islamic teachings. While the use of exaggeration and embellishment to enhance sales is a common practice in the industry, faithful business owners are reminded of the Islamic prohibition against any form of deception in trade. Deception is defined as the use of cunning tactics for personal gain at the expense

of others, and it encompasses various unethical practices such as falsifying signatures, selling counterfeit goods at inflated prices, or deceiving customers through false advertisements. Even invoking the name of Allah to bolster sales while misrepresenting the truth is considered deceptive, as highlighted by Prophet Muhammad's warnings against excessive swearing in business transactions. This serves as a reminder to business owners of the spiritual consequences of engaging in deceptive practices and underscores the importance of maintaining integrity and truthfulness in all aspects of commerce, in accordance with Islamic principles. By adhering to the values of honesty and transparency, businesses can uphold their ethical standards and foster trust and credibility among consumers within Islamic contexts.

Avoiding Disclosure of Faults

Avoiding disclosure of faults in hijack marketing entails ensuring that businesses obtain proper consent from individuals or parties whose situations are being utilized for promotional purposes. This involves seeking permission and informing the concerned parties beforehand to mitigate the risk of legal claims or reputational damage. Additionally, it's important to consider situations where incidents occur without the knowledge or consent of the individuals involved, emphasizing the need for ethical consideration and sensitivity in such cases. Drawing upon the teachings of Prophet Muhammad, who praised those who conceal the faults of their fellow believers, businesses are reminded of the importance of integrity and compassion in their marketing practices. This principle underscores the significance of respecting the dignity and privacy of individuals, while also recognizing the potential consequences of exploiting or publicizing sensitive situations without proper consent. By prioritizing ethical conduct and respecting the rights of others, businesses can uphold their reputation and foster trust among consumers within Islamic contexts.

Ensuring Cultural Sensitivity and Contextual Relevance

Ensuring cultural sensitivity and contextual relevance in marketing involves crafting messages and campaigns that align with the target audience's cultural and religious values, norms, and sensitivities, particularly within Islamic communities. This entails conducting thorough research to understand the diverse perspectives, traditions, and practices within these communities and recognizing the significance of religious events, holidays, and cultural celebrations. By doing so, businesses can tailor their marketing strategies to resonate with the target audience, using language, imagery, and themes that are appropriate and respectful. Additionally, cultural sensitivity involves avoiding stereotypes, misconceptions, or generalizations that may offend or alienate the audience. Instead, marketers should strive to authentically connect with consumers, acknowledging their unique identities and experiences. On the other hand, contextual relevance emphasizes the importance of considering the broader socio-political, economic, and environmental factors that shape the local context in which the marketing campaign operates. This may include addressing relevant social issues, economic challenges, or prevalent cultural trends within the target market. Overall, ensuring cultural sensitivity and contextual relevance in marketing enables businesses to build meaningful relationships with consumers, foster trust and loyalty, and effectively engage with diverse audiences within Islamic communities.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

In conclusion, this study underscores the viability of hijack marketing from a Sharia-compliant perspective, provided it adheres to Islamic principles of honesty, integrity, and respect for others. Businesses can effectively leverage hijack marketing while upholding ethical standards by ensuring clear and accurate information, obtaining consent from involved parties, maintaining respect for

human dignity, and emphasizing social responsibility. This approach fosters trust among consumers, promotes positive societal values, and demonstrates a commitment to conducting business by Islamic teachings. Therefore, businesses and marketers should prioritize Sharia-compliant practices in their marketing strategies, recognizing the importance of ethical conduct and transparency in engaging with customers and the broader community.

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